

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society programme under grant agreement no. 872483

Project acronym:

DocEnhance

Project title:

“Enhancing skills intelligence and integration into existing PhD programmes by providing transferable skills training through an open online platform”

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Report from the Stakeholder Validation Workshop

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² PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specifies by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	15/07/2022	María Soledad Pastor	Draft version for DocEnhance partners' review

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1. MAIN EVALUATION OUTCOMES FROM BREAK-OUT GROUP DISCUSSIONS

General satisfaction with course design, structure and content

Positive feedback was received from participants in the Stakeholder Validation Workshop (SVW) regarding the design, structure and content of the three DocEnhance pilot courses to be validated: Supervision, Data Stewardship, and Career Management and Entrepreneurship.

Suggestions for course improvement

Participants pointed out areas of improvement with regards to the course curriculum:

- Supervision course
 - Include a teaching guide explaining the purpose of the supervision course, to be adapted by each University.
 - Detail the desired/recommended profile (skills, competences, personal and professional qualities) to be met by the trainers conducting the supervision course, especially if course participants are senior supervisors.
 - Provide a repository of course OERs.
 - Maintain the variety of materials, resources and activities, as well as the possibilities for a flexible use and adaptation of the materials.
 - Classify activities (using a colour code) depending on the intended target group and use of the materials.
 - Promote collaborative and interactive approaches for most of the course activities.
 - Include samples of activities with guidelines/videos on how they should be carried out.
 - Include peer assessment and oral presentations as possible activities to be carried out by the participating supervisors at the end of the course.
- Data Stewardship course
 - A greater focus on the issue of Data Validation.
 - Include FAIR principles in the course's expected learning outcomes.
 - Cooperation with the industry/business sectors and/or public services in Module 3.
- Career Management and Entrepreneurship course
 - Include a section on self-branding ("Framing your skills")
 - Include tips on how to write a CV/different kind of CVs and cover letters
 - Support videos with short written material
 - Provide guidelines for self-assessment
 - Include interactive assignments
 - Include online material with young entrepreneurs
 - Provide a link to Nature Career's materials on mentoring

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- Include a repository with useful resources
- Provide guidelines for teachers/trainers on how to: run the course (in-person and/or online); run each module; apply the resources provided for different types of activities; contact the industry/non-academic sector and young entrepreneurs in order to facilitate career development through visits in and interaction with external actors

1.2. MAIN EVALUATION OUTCOMES FROM POST-WORKSHOP QUESTIONNAIRES

General satisfaction with Stakeholder Validation Workshop and DocEnhance platform

Positive feedback was received from participants in the SVW regarding the workshop itself, stating that it provided “a lot of food for thought”. Nevertheless, several respondents thought that the workshop was a bit short, especially the parallel break-out sessions, and that adding 1 or 2 hours for deeper discussion would have been a good idea.

The different aspects of the workshop were generally rated as excellent. The highest global ratings went to interest of the topics discussed, moderators' knowledge of the subject, usefulness of the topics addressed, and level of personal satisfaction. The lowest global rating went to the workshop duration.

With respect to the DocEnhance platform, respondents unanimously applauded the initiative and reported to be satisfied with the majority of the aspects assessed. The lowest rating went to level of satisfaction when searching for information.

Suggestions for improvement

Suggestions for future stakeholder workshops included discussions on research ethics, competitive calls and marketing strategies for the platform, as well as a networking session with stakeholders to foster relationships between academia and industry

Regarding the DocEnhance Platform, several respondents called for a forum for learners and teachers to post questions and comments, and to interact. Respondents also suggested that there should be a bigger mix of learning materials in different formats, and that more videos be included to support the use of the links provided, in particular videos with extensive explanations on how to license content or share data correctly. Respondents also called for the convenience of including the number of course hours or ECTS in the module certificates. It was also suggested that users be given the possibility of logging in via ORCID or via institution without having to create a new account. One respondent believed that the platform could be structured more clearly and another called for some mechanism to provide different access for trainer materials.

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2. INTRODUCTION

On June 22nd, 2022, the DocEnhance consortium held the Stakeholder Validation Workshop (SVW) at the University of Manchester (Manchester, UK), in the frame of the project's second annual meeting and the [EUA-CDE Annual Meeting](#), with the double objective of:

- presenting the second prototype of the DocEnhance Platform and its revised contents (the three transferable skills courses designed and piloted by different consortium members on Supervision, Data Management, and Career Management and Entrepreneurship) to interested stakeholders, and
- collecting vital external feedback and suggestions regarding its usefulness, usability and possible areas of improvement.

In order to facilitate stakeholder participation in the in-person workshop, DocEnhance offered a number of travel grants of up to 750 € to cover travel and accommodation expenses, to be paid after the workshop upon presentation of the corresponding invoice and supporting documents. 18 participants initially applied for the travel grants when pre-registering for the workshop. A total of 7 travel grants were finally awarded to participating stakeholders.

43 pre-registrations were received, of which 32 participated in the workshop: 13 external stakeholders and 19 consortium members. Participants represented institutions from 14 countries: Austria (1), Belgium (2), Croatia (1), Czech Republic (3), Finland (1), France (1), Germany (1), Greece (2), Ireland (1), Norway (8), Portugal (2), Spain (6), Switzerland (2) and United Kingdom (1).

The institutional profile of participants was predominately academic (72% universities), although the non-profit sector was also well represented (25%). The business sector accounted for 3% of represented institutions.

Participants' professional profile was diverse, including for example: PhD candidate, professor/lecturer, senior advisor, project manager, CEO, data analyst and developer, researcher, doctoral school or programme staff, career specialist.

The workshop was held in-person with the following agenda:

- 09:00-09:05 Welcome
Alexander Hasgall, Head of the EUA Council for Doctoral Education and DocEnhance External Advisor
- 09:05-09:10 The DocEnhance project
Hanne Risan Johnsen, DocEnhance Project Coordinator (UIT)

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09:10-09:20 The DocEnhance Platform: a brief overview

Fabiana Minneci (EUJ)

Evangelos Chondrokostas (AUn)

09:20-10:45 Stakeholder discussions

Break-out group 1: Supervision Course

Moderators: Alfredo Gardel (UAH) and Alberto Lázaro (UAH)

Break-out group 2: Data Stewardship Course

Moderators: Filip Faltejsek (UCT) and Leif Longva (UIT)

Break-out group 3: Career Management and Entrepreneurship Course

Moderators: Elsa Caetano (UNL) and Michaela Aschan (UIT)

10:45-11:00 Preliminary conclusions by Moderators

Break-out group moderators, together with the DocEnhance coordinator and WP leaders, agreed upon a common set of questions to be posed to participants in order to facilitate and dynamise the group discussions:

- What learning outcomes should be expected from this course?
- What are your expectations regarding the course?
- How does the course align with the learning outcomes and your expectations?
- Do you think that the course design, contents, methodology, learning materials and guidelines facilitate the expected learning outcomes?
- When you look at the curriculum, is there anything you feel is missing?
- Is there anything you consider superfluous?
- How can we improve these aspects of the course?
- What is your opinion regarding the usability and functionality of the DocEnhance Platform?

It was agreed that more specific questions would be made in line with participant profiles in each break-out group.

Prior to the SVW celebration, registered participants received an informed consent form (See Annex I) which included an information sheet on the workshop and a certificate of consent, to be signed by those planning to participate in the session.

They also received a pre-workshop information package (see Annex II) including a brief overview of the DocEnhance project and workshop objectives, a summary of the DocEnhance transferable skills courses, and instructions on how to register and log into the DocEnhance platform in order to facilitate their knowledge of the platform and its contents, and to ensure a fluid and dynamic discussion during the session.

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After the SVW, and in order to complement the information gathered during the workshop discussions, the 19 external stakeholders participating in the workshop were invited to complete two brief questionnaires (see Annex III) on 1) different aspects of the workshop organization, content and development and 2) the DocEnhance Platform. The collection of data was carried out online (Google Forms) and the responses collected were anonymous. 43,8% completed the questionnaires.

The SVW questionnaires were the same as those used after the Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop held in September 2021, in order to facilitate possible comparison of results.

The questionnaires were organised in a given set of close-ended and open-ended questions.

The response options for a closed-ended question were exhaustive and mutually exclusive. The types of response for closed-ended questions are rate scale responses presented with a continuous scale based on 5 levels and referred to:

- Workshop: practical organisation of the workshop; moderators; workshop content and development; interest and usefulness of the workshop: and level of satisfaction.
- DocEnhance Platform: readability; navigation; search engine; graphic design; loading speed; and level of satisfaction.

Open-ended questions ask respondents to formulate his/her own answer in his/her own words, including comments and/or suggestions for improvement, referring to:

- Workshop: most and least interesting topics addressed; additional topics for inclusion in future stakeholder workshops; and usefulness.
- DocEnhance Platform: functionalities and usefulness.

Feedback gathered from the SVW discussions and questionnaires, together with the evaluation of the second implementation of the pilot courses will be taken into consideration when further refining the course concept and content and further development of the DocEnhance platform.

3. FEEDBACK FROM BREAK-OUT GROUP DISCUSSIONS

Qualitative results are presented separately for each course based on the notes taken by the break-out group moderators during the group discussions.

3.1. BREAK-OUT GROUP 1: SUPERVISION

After a short introduction on the Supervision course by the group moderators and a brief presentation of participating stakeholders, the discussion began with a short brainstorming session on the course guidelines and materials, access to the platform and intended usage of the OERs available on the DocEnhance LMS. It became clear from the participants' feedback that more efforts should be taken to better clarify how trainers should reuse the OER materials available on the LMS platform.

Participants were later split into two smaller groups in order to discuss general questions regarding the course.

The following suggestions were extracted from the group discussions:

- Include a teaching guide explaining the purpose of the supervision course, to be adapted by each University.
- Detail the desired/recommended profile (skills, competences, personal and professional qualities) to be met by the trainers conducting the supervision course, especially if course participants are senior supervisors.
- Provide a repository of course OERs. This suggestion is in line with the opinion of stakeholders participating in the Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop (September 2021) when they considered that the course “should be considered to be more like a resource bank than closed course material designed to be implemented, for example, linearly following the content order.”
- Maintain the variety of materials, resources and activities, as well as the possibilities for a flexible use and adaptation of the materials. It was pointed out that while some activities are more appropriate for junior supervisors, others are better for senior supervisors, or even mixed groups. Participants proposed that activities could be classified (using a colour code) depending on the intended target group (junior or senior supervisors) and the use of the materials (group activities, individual work, assessment). This idea was also expressed in the Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop held in September 2021, when participants pointed out that “it is essential to include clear guidelines on the DocEnhance platform with information/instructions on how to use the material for different target groups (for example, junior or senior supervisors)”.

- Promote collaborative and interactive approaches for most of the course activities.
- Include samples of activities with guidelines/videos on how they should be carried out.
- Include peer assessment and oral presentations as possible activities to be carried out by the participating supervisors at the end of the course.
- Mixed groups are suggested whenever possible.
- Offer some certification, or charter mark, that maps to the European Commission Horizon Europe pillars, the Gender Equity Plan and the SDGs.

3.2. BREAK-GROUP 2: DATA STEWARDSHIP

A short presentation of the course content and expected learning outcomes, was followed by a presentation of how the second pilot run was done at UCT. Issues related to the theory and best practice of data management were discussed, as well as recommendations on the practical implementation of the course based on the experience of the second pilot run at UCT.

Participants discussed the issue of the course's timing in depth. Regarding Module 1, they believed that students need at least two weeks, or even a month, for proper completion. Participants pointed out that it could be very motivating for the students to have their own data when joining Module 2. This would mean enrolling in Module 2 quite a bit later than completing Module 1. If there is a lengthy period between the completion of Module 1 and the start of Module 2, some repetition of Module 1 was recommended. Participants also pointed out that perhaps the candidates should be given the option to take the Module 1 exam again, to test their theory knowledge, before entering Module 2.

A greater focus on the issue of Data Validation was called for by participants. A core issue of data validation is to do a cleaning process to make sure the data values are valid. There are methods to check for obvious typos. One example is to sort a column of numerical values in ascending and descending order, to discover invalid values or values out of scope. This issue of data cleaning is included in the course (section 7 of Module 1: "Data cleaning, analysis and visualization"), but perhaps this section should include the notion of 'Data validation' in the title.

Participants also suggested that FAIR principles be included in the course's expected learning outcomes, as they are at the core of most aspects of data stewardship.

With respect to Module 3, participants highlighted the fact that it is a very flexible module and pointed out the assignments should be designed and described in cooperation with the businesses or public services who participate in the Module. Recruiting industry or

public services to join in on Module 3 is a challenge. These external parties need to see a benefit for themselves in order to find it worthwhile to participate. A valid incentive for them may be the opportunity to meet and get to know PhD candidates that potentially may be job applicants in the near future, inviting them to define their PhD research project using data from the industry or public service in question. In this way, both the PhD candidate and the industry/public service could mutually benefit directly from their cooperation in Module 3. This reflection was in line with the conclusions reached in the data stewardship break-out group held during the Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop in September 2021, when participants suggested that “students carry out assignments in cooperation with the non-academic sector (business, industry, public sector, etc.) in Module 3”.

BREAK-OUT GROUP 3: CAREER MANAGEMENT AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP

The content of the Career Management and Entrepreneurship course was considered to be too much to cover in one single course. Potential students should know beforehand how much time is needed to complete the full course.

Participants suggested that the course be split into two separate courses: one on career development/management (identify your opportunities) and another on entrepreneurship. If the course can not be split into two, participants suggested that the course title be changed to “Career Management” as the term “entrepreneurship” is not inviting for all PhD candidates, in particular those from the humanities and social sciences disciplines. In this case, the material on entrepreneurship mindset could be used as a tool for career management.

At any rate, participants believed that the career management part of the course should be offered in the first stages of the doctoral process, and the entrepreneurship part should be taken closer to the dissertation or in the postdoc stage.

Participants pointed out that career management/development is not suited for completely online training and also addressed the need to add or improve some contents:

- Include a section on self-branding (“Framing your skills”). PhD candidates are often not aware of their competencies, so it is necessary to help them identify and document their skills and opportunities, and effectively communicate their talent to non-academic recruiters.
- Include tips on how to write a CV/different kinds of CVs and cover letters and on how to answer common interview questions.
- Support videos with short written material, and provide at least the key messages from each video as bullet points.
- Provide guidelines for self-assessment.

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- Include interactive assignments, especially if the course is online, in order to keep students motivated.
- Include online material with young entrepreneurs (for example, webinars with short talks by entrepreneurs hosted by Karolinska Institutet).
- Provide a link to Nature Career's materials on mentoring (<https://www.nature.com/collections/lhgrjpydm/>)
- Include a repository with useful resources.

Participants also called for the need to provide clear guidelines for teachers/trainers on how to:

- Run the course (in-person and/or online) and each module
- Apply the resources provided for group activities, individual work, self-assessment, etc.
- Contact the industry/non-academic sector and young entrepreneurs with the objective of facilitating career development through visits in and interaction with external actors (local industry, university alumni, entrepreneur networks, etc.). This point was also brought up during the Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop held in September 2021 when participants "called for a more experiential approach in the mobility module in order to clearly identify the differences between working in the academic or non-academic sectors, to improve the exchange of perspectives between both sectors, and to promote technology transfer carried out by PhDs."

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4. FEEDBACK FROM POST-WORKSHOP QUESTIONNAIRES

As already mentioned above in the INTRODUCTION, stakeholders participating in the workshop discussions were invited to complete two brief questionnaires on different aspects of the workshop (organization, moderators, content and development, interest and usefulness, level of satisfaction) and the DocEnhance Platform (readability, navigation, search engine, graphic design, loading speed, functionalities, usefulness, and level of satisfaction).

43,8% of workshop participants completed the questionnaires.

4.1. WORKSHOP QUESTIONNAIRE

Participants were asked to mark the rating that best reflected their opinion on each of the aspects to be assessed. The ratings were on a scale of 1 to 5 (1: very poor, 2: poor; 3: good; 4: very good; 5: excellent).

The different aspects of the workshop were generally rated as excellent. The highest global ratings went to interest of the topics discussed (4,79), moderators' knowledge of the subject (4,71), usefulness of the topics addressed (4,57), and level of personal satisfaction (4,47). The lowest global rating went to the workshop duration (3,79).

Formal Aspects	1	2	3	4	5	Global score
Workshop organisation	0,0	7,1	0,0	28,6	64,3	4,50
Online connection	0,0	0,0	14,3	28,6	57,1	4,43
Programme compliance	0,0	7,1	0,0	42,9	50,0	4,36
Total	0,0	4,8	4,8	33,3	57,1	4,43

Moderators	1	2	3	4	5	Global score
Communication / interaction with participants	0,0	0,0	14,3	28,6	57,1	4,43
Amenity of the presentations	0,0	0,0	14,3	21,4	64,3	4,50
Knowledge of the subject	0,0	0,0	0,0	28,6	71,4	4,71
Total	0,0	0,0	9,5	26,2	64,3	4,55

Content and Development	1	2	3	4	5	Global score
Duration	0,0	0,0	7,1	28,6	64,3	3,79
Usefulness of topics addressed	0,0	0,0	0,0	21,4	78,6	4,57
Interest of topics addressed	0,0	7,1	7,1	21,4	64,3	4,79
Clarity and quality of contents	0,0	0,0	21,4	21,4	57,1	4,43
Interactive discussions	0,0	2,9	14,3	24,3	58,6	4,36
Total	0,0	0,0	7,1	28,6	64,3	4,39

Other Aspects	1	2	3	4	5	Global score
Interest and usefulness of the workshop	0,0	0,0	14,3	28,6	57,1	4,43
Level of personal satisfaction	0,0	0,0	7,1	28,6	64,3	4,57
Total	0,0	0,0	10,7	28,6	60,7	4,50

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Most aspects evaluated improved slightly (between 0,03 and 0,38 points) in comparison with results obtained after the Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop held in September 2021, except for communication/interaction with participants (-0,07), interest and usefulness of the workshop (-0,07) and duration (-0,38).

Formal Aspects	Global score SEW 2021	Global score SVW 2022	Variation 2021-2022
Workshop organisation	4,33	4,50	+ 0,17
Online connection	4,33	4,43	+ 0,10
Programme compliance	4,17	4,36	+ 0,19
Total	4,28	4,43	+ 0,15

Moderators	Global score SEW 2021	Global score SVW 2022	Variation 2021-2022
Communication / interaction with participants	4,50	4,43	- 0,07
Amenity of the presentations	4,17	4,50	+ 0,33
Knowledge of the subject	4,67	4,71	+ 0,04
Total	4,44	4,55	+ 0,11

Content and Development	Global score SEW 2021	Global score SVW 2022	Variation 2021-2022
Duration	4,17	3,79	- 0,38
Usefulness of topics addressed	4,33	4,57	+ 0,24
Interest of topics addressed	4,50	4,79	+ 0,29
Clarity and quality of contents	4,17	4,43	+ 0,26
Interactive discussions	4,33	4,36	+ 0,03
Total	4,30	4,39	+ 0,09

Other Aspects	Global score SEW 2021	Global score SVW 2022	Variation 2021-2022
Interest and usefulness of the workshop	4,50	4,43	- 0,07
Level of personal satisfaction	4,33	4,57	+ 0,24
Total	4,42	4,50	+ 0,08

Respondents believed that the workshop provided “a lot of food for thought”. Several respondents thought that the workshop was a bit short, especially the parallel break-out sessions, and that adding 1 or 2 hours for deeper discussion would have been a good idea.

When asked to identify the most interesting topics addressed in the workshop, respondents mentioned the opening presentations by Alexander Hasgall and Hanne Risan Johnsen), the parallel sessions’ conclusions, career tracking survey results, usability and users’ experience, career management and entrepreneurial mindset, licensing procedures, and metadata sharing in open databases.

Suggestions for future stakeholder workshops included discussions on research ethics, competitive calls and marketing strategies for the platform, as well as a networking session with stakeholders to foster relationships between academia and industry. One respondent suggested that moderators send guidelines for discussion before the workshop.

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4.2. PLATFORM QUESTIONNAIRE

Participants were asked to mark the rating that best reflected their opinion on each of the aspects to be assessed. The ratings were on a scale of 1 to 5 (1: very dissatisfied, 2: dissatisfied; 3: enough satisfied; 4: satisfied; 5: very satisfied).

In general, respondents reported to be satisfied (between 4,00 and 4,50) with the majority of the aspects assessed. The lowest rating went to level of satisfaction when searching for information (3,86).

	1	2	3	4	5	Global score
To what extent is the Platform's content readable and viewable for you?	0,0	14,3	7,1	14,3	64,3	4,29
To what degree do you consider the information comprehensible instantly?	0,0	14,3	14,3	28,6	42,9	4,00
Qualify your level of satisfaction when searching for any kind of information.	0,0	7,1	42,9	7,1	42,9	3,86
To what degree is the navigation simple and comprehensible?	0,0	7,1	14,3	21,4	57,1	4,29
How much does the graphic design fulfil your expectations or meet your requirements?	0,0	7,1	7,1	42,9	42,9	4,21
Evaluate the speed by which the elements are loaded	0,0	0,0	7,1	35,7	57,1	4,50
Level of general satisfaction	0,0	14,3	7,1	14,3	64,3	4,29
Total	0,0	9,2	14,3	23,5	53,1	4,20

All aspects evaluated improved between 0,29 and 0,78 points in comparison with results obtained after the Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop held in September 2021, except for level of satisfaction when searching for information which remained unaltered.

	Global score SEW 2021	Global score SVW 2022	Variation 2021-2022
To what extent is the Platform's content readable and viewable for you?	4,00	4,29	+ 0,29
To what degree do you consider the information comprehensible instantly?	3,43	4,00	+ 0,57
Qualify your level of satisfaction when searching for any kind of information.	3,86	3,86	==
To what degree is the navigation simple and comprehensible?	4,00	4,29	+ 0,29
How much does the graphic design fulfil your expectations or meet your requirements?	3,43	4,21	+ 0,78
Evaluate the speed by which the elements are loaded	4,00	4,50	+ 0,50
Level of general satisfaction	4,00	4,29	+ 0,29
Total	3,81	4,20	+ 0,39

When asked if they would include/exclude/edit any functionality to the DocEnhance Platform, as occurred with the questionnaire sent out after the Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop held in September 2021, several respondents called for a forum or messaging system for learners and teachers to post questions and comments, and to interact. It was

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also suggested that users be given the possibility of logging in via ORCID or via institution without having to create a new account. One respondent believed that the platform could be structured more clearly and another called for some mechanism to provide different access for trainer materials.

Respondents suggested that there should be a bigger mix of learning materials in different formats, and that more videos be included to support the use of the links provided, in particular videos with extensive explanations on how to license content or share data correctly. A respondent also suggested that it would be useful to complement the videos with a digital handbook with subheadings and key summaries of each video's subsections.

Some suggested that the UN Global Competences and SDGs be linked to the competences that are meant to be gained through the courses.

Respondents also called for the convenience of including the number of course hours or ECTS in the module certificates.

With regards to the usefulness of the DocEnhance Platform for the respondents' sectors or institutions, they unanimously applauded the initiative, as they did when responding the questionnaire sent out after the Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop.

One respondent pointed out that all materials were incredibly useful and that the videos were outstanding, in particular the video "What is Supervision Path, Environment and Space".

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5. ANNEX I: INFORMED CONSENT FORM

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This informed consent form is for stakeholders, who are invited to participate in the DocEnhance Stakeholder Validation Workshop organized by Fundación Universidad-Empresa.

Name of Organization: Fundación Universidad-Empresa
Name of Contact Person: Marisol Pastor
Name of Project: DocEnhance GA872483 H2020-SwafS-2019-1

This Informed Consent Form has two parts:

- Information Sheet (to share information about the workshop with you)
- Certificate of Consent (for signatures if you choose to participate)

You will be given a copy of the full Informed Consent Form

Part I: Information Sheet

Introduction

The DocEnhance project aims to enhance skills intelligence and integration into existing PhD programmes in Europe, and to increase interaction and exposure to the non-academic sector. To achieve this, the project is developing a series of transferable skills courses, a recommended PhD curriculum for Higher Education Institutions, and an online platform.

Information on the DocEnhance project is available on <https://docenhance.eu/>

Fundación Universidad-Empresa is involved in the DocEnhance project and as part of this project we would like to give you information on the Stakeholder Validation Workshop we will be holding on June 22nd, 2022. If you have questions about the workshop, you can write to us at docenhance.cde-workshop@fue.es

Purpose of the workshop

The workshop will present the second prototype of the DocEnhance Platform and its revised course contents to interested stakeholders, with the objective of collecting vital feedback and suggestions regarding its usefulness, usability and possible areas of improvement.

Participants will receive relevant information before the workshop in order to ensure a fluid and dynamic discussion during the workshop.

Workshop Development

- A. This workshop consists of small group discussions. Your participation will help us to provide a useful platform where academic and non-academic actors may have the opportunity to connect and access the different resources (course, guidelines, reports and studies) created through the project. In this way you will contribute to improving PhD graduates' employability through innovative transferable skills training.
- B. The workshop discussions will be recorded to facilitate the elaboration of recommendations and conclusions and organizers may take photographs of the sessions.
- C. After the workshop, you will be invited to fill out an evaluation questionnaire by Fundación Universidad-Empresa. The questionnaire is to be filled out online and the questions asked will concern different aspects of the workshop organization, content and development. You will also receive a questionnaire regarding the DocEnhance Platform.

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When and Where

The workshop will be held on June 22nd, 2022, from 09:00 to 11:00 CET at the University of Manchester (University Place, 176 Oxford Place, Manchester UK).

Risks

The workshop and evaluation questionnaire will not address any sensitive information (e.g. political opinions or community beliefs) and the confidentiality arrangements in place will guarantee that any potentially identifying data collected (e.g. e-mail) will be anonymized before the elaboration of workshop recommendations and conclusions.

Reimbursements

Participation to the DocEnhance workshop is open to all interested parties and is free of charge. You will therefore not receive any monetary reimbursement for your participation.

Travel Grants

DocEnhance will be funding a number of travel grants to facilitate stakeholder participation in the workshop. You may apply for a travel grant when registering for the workshop. Travel grants will be awarded on a first come first served basis and will cover up to 750 € of travel and accommodation expenses and will be paid upon presentation of the corresponding invoice and supporting documents.

Confidentiality

Fundación Universidad-Empresa will receive your contact information (e-mail) from the workshop registration form. The contact information provided will only be used for the purposes of DocEnhance workshop organization and follow-up. The evaluation questionnaire will be anonymous and will not seek any personally identifiable information.

Sharing the Results

The knowledge that we gain from this workshop will be shared with you and will also be made available to the public, including via the DocEnhance website. Each participant will receive a summary of the workshop conclusions.

Who to Contact

If you have any questions about this workshop, please contact Fundación Universidad-Empresa at docenhance.cde-workshop@fue.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society programme under grant agreement no. 872483

Part II: Certificate of Consent

I have been invited to participate in the Docenhance Stakeholder Validation Workshop and am participating in this event to contribute to enabling higher education institutions to adjust their curricula with relevant and up-to-date skills.

I have read the foregoing information. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this workshop.

Print name of participant _____

Signature of participant _____

Date _____
Day/month/year

I confirm that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this ICF has been provided to the participant.

Print name of organizer taking the consent _____

Signature of organizer taking the consent _____

Date _____
Day/month/year

|

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6. ANNEX II: PRE-WORKSHOP INFORMATION PACKAGE

PRE-WORKSHOP INFORMATION FOR PARTICIPANTS 22 June 2022

The DocEnhance project

DocEnhance is a three-year project (January 2020 - December 2022) funded by the EU Horizon 2020 programme and aims to enhance transferable skills intelligence and integration into existing PhD programmes by:

- developing an employment and innovation-oriented curriculum for PhD programmes,
- facilitating business-education partnerships,
- tracking PhD graduate career paths.

The major outputs of the project are:

- a recommended transferable skills curriculum for PhD programmes,
- a new course concept and material,
- an open access career-tracking survey.

These outputs will be provided as Open Educational Resources (OER) through an online platform, the DocEnhance Platform (DEP).

For more information, please visit the [DocEnhance website](#).

About the workshop

The DocEnhance Stakeholder Validation Workshop will be held on Wednesday, 22nd June 2022, from 09:00 to 11:00 CET, at the University of Manchester (University Place, 176 Oxford Road, Manchester UK). It will bring together international academic and non-academic actors in the frame of the EUA-CDE Annual Meeting and will provide an opportunity to present the work carried out so far by the consortium, discuss the main outcomes and ask for your feedback on how to improve them.

Main focus

During the workshop, the second prototype of the DocEnhance Platform (DEP) will be presented to you as well as the content of the three courses: (I) PhD Supervision, (II) Data Stewardship, (III) Career management and Entrepreneurship.

To better prepare for our discussion during the workshop and ensure your active involvement, we have prepared the short information guide that follows. We hope this information will be helpful!

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INFORMATION GUIDE

Transferable skills courses

The project focuses on transferable skills, as these skills facilitate the transition into employment and are widely applicable, regardless of the scientific field and chosen career path. The following transferable skills pilot courses are being created:

Course in Data Stewardship

As research data becomes more openly available, data stewardship is a skill in high demand, both within and beyond academia.

DocEnhance provides a course for PhDs to master theory and concepts of data management, and to learn how to collect, analyse and manage research data. This theoretical course is completed with hands-on digital skills training, and on-site practical assignments in non-academic settings.

Course in Supervision

The quality of supervision is one of the most important factors in a successful PhD graduation. This affects not only the quality and content of the research output but also the completion rate, time to completion, student satisfaction, mental health, and future career prospects.

DocEnhance provides a course for supervisors and trainers to (1) identify and embed pedagogical, practical and up-to-date skills in supervision, (2) know how to implement them in context, (3) master up-to-date research skills elements, (4) discover peer supervision, (5) adapt supervision practices.

Course in Career Management and Entrepreneurship

Research careers are rarely a single, predetermined path. A successful career involves being prepared to deviate from previous paths and explore entirely new options, and this does not always come readily. An under-exploited career path is entrepreneurship, requiring specific competencies.

DocEnhance provides a course for PhDs to learn how to: (1) reflect upon personal strengths, weaknesses and life goals, (2) develop critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication and self-management skills, (3) act upon entrepreneurial ideas and opportunities and transform them into value by mobilising resources and networks.

More information on the courses at <https://courses.docenhance.eu/>

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The DocEnhance Platform (DEP)

The three above-mentioned courses and all DocEnhance Open Education Resources will be hosted in the [DocEnhance Platform](#), designed to provide an interdisciplinary space for cooperation and information sharing with the aim of supporting innovative career-oriented PhD training. It will provide academic and non-academic actors with the opportunity to connect and access the different resources (courses, guidelines, reports and studies) created through the project.

Watch the video to know more about the platform! Click [here](#).

Please kindly note that improvements over the second release of the platform and courses will be made during the project lifetime.

Registration and log-in

Please make sure to complete the login process before the workshop, following the steps below.

1. The first step is to visit the DocEnhance Platform at <https://courses.docenhance.eu/>
2. Click the 'Log in' button, in the top right corner.
3. To use the DocEnhance platform's full functionality, you will need to create an account on PhD Hub. Please choose the 'login with PhDHub' option.
4. By clicking on 'login with PhDHub' you will be redirected to the PhD Hub login (<https://phdhub.eu/login/>). Click on 'You don't have an account? Create one now!'
5. Fill in the registration form at <https://phdhub.eu/register/>. You can choose to create an account using your personal or institutional email. Please note that this step is only required to perform once.
6. Once you are registered, activate your account via the link sent to your email address.
7. Congratulations! Now that the registration process has been completed, you can log in to the DocEnhance Platform at <https://courses.docenhance.eu/login/>. Please remember to choose the 'login with PhDHub' option.

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7. ANNEX III: EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRES

7.1. DOCENHANCE STAKEHOLDER VALIDATION WORKSHOP EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE

DOCENHANCE STAKEHOLDER VALIDATION WORKSHOP JUNE 22, 2022

This questionnaire is designed to obtain your opinion on the Workshop in which you have participated, in order to evaluate its quality and identify possible areas of improvement.

Please mark with an X the rating that best reflects your opinion on each of the aspects to be assessed (1: very poor, 5: excellent).

Thank you for your collaboration.

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Poor	Very poor
FORMAL ASPECTS					
Organisation	5	4	3	2	1
Quality of the online connection	5	4	3	2	1
Programme compliance	5	4	3	2	1
MODERATORS					
Communication / interaction with participants	5	4	3	2	1
Amenity of the presentations	5	4	3	2	1
Knowledge of the subject	5	4	3	2	1
CONTENT AND DEVELOPMENT					
Duration	5	4	3	2	1
Interest of topics addressed					
Usefulness of topics addressed	5	4	3	2	1
Clarity and quality of contents	5	4	3	2	1
Interactive discussions	5	4	3	2	1
OTHER ASPECTS					
Interest and usefulness of the Workshop	5	4	3	2	1
Level of personal satisfaction	5	4	3	2	1

What were the most interesting topics addressed in the workshop? Why?

And the least interesting? Why?

Would you include any additional topics in future stakeholder workshops? If so, please specify.

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Are the workshop conclusions useful for your institution and sector? Why? Would you include/exclude/edit any functionality to the DocEnhance Platform? If so, please specify.

Comments/Suggestions

7.2. DOCENHANCE PLATFORM EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE

DOCENHANCE STAKEHOLDER VALIDATION WORKSHOP JUNE 22, 2022

This questionnaire is designed to obtain your opinion on the DocEnhance Platform, in order to evaluate its quality and identify possible areas of improvement.

Please mark with an X the rating that best reflects your opinion on each of the aspects to be assessed (1: very dissatisfied, 5: very satisfied).

Thank you for your collaboration.

	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Enough satisfied	Dissatisfied	Very dissatisfied
Specify to what extent is the DocEnhance Platform's content readable and viewable for you.	5	4	3	2	1
To what degree do you consider the information comprehensible instantly?	5	4	3	2	1
Qualify your level of satisfaction when searching for any kind of information. <i>(It does not matter if you finally found what you were looking for).</i>	5	4	3	2	1
Specify to what degree is the navigation simple and comprehensible.	5	4	3	2	1
How much does the graphic design fulfil your expectations or meet your requirements?	5	4	3	2	1
Evaluate the speed by which the elements are loaded.	5	4	3	2	1
Level of general satisfaction.	5	4	3	2	1

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Would you include/exclude/edit any functionality to the DocEnhance Platform? If so, please specify.

Is the DocEnhance Platform useful for your sector or institution? Why?

Comments/Suggestions